

D7.2 COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION PLAN V2 INCLUDING CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES

WP7, T7.1

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TECHNICAL REFERENCES

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- SEN= sensitive

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ACRONYMS

C&D: Communication and Dissemination
 WP: Work Package
 KER: Key Exploitable Result
 KPI: Key Performance Indicator
 CEI: Community Engagement Index
 PEI: Publication Engagement Index
 SEI: Social Engagement Index
 WEI: Website Engagement Index

1. INTRODUCTION

This document presents the updated Communication and Dissemination (C&D) strategy of the SPOON project, building on the framework established in the initial plan (D7.1). While the first version defined the overall approach and key principles, **this update reflects the project's progress** and integrates insights gained from the implementation of activities to date.

The objective of this document is to **refine and operationalise the C&D strategy** for the upcoming phases, ensuring alignment with project goals while adapting to emerging needs and opportunities. Particular attention is given to the development of a multi-level strategy that ensures coherence at the EU level while allowing adaptation to local contexts through the involvement of Local Desks.

A key element of this updated strategy is the systematic **monitoring of communication and dissemination performance**. The analysis of key indicators has provided evidence on what works most effectively in terms of outreach and engagement, allowing the project to refine its approach and prioritise the most impactful content types and formats.

The strategy also reinforces the role of **clustering activities** as a key mechanism to enhance knowledge transfer, create synergies with related initiatives, and maximise the impact of project results.

Finally, the Communication and Dissemination Plan is closely linked to the ongoing assessment of **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)**, which are continuously monitored to identify the most relevant outcomes to be disseminated. This ensures that communication efforts remain targeted, impactful, and aligned with the project's innovation potential.

2. PROGRESS REPORT

2.1 MONITORING ACTIVITY

SPOON's communication activities are continuously monitored to assess their overall performance and effectiveness. This monitoring process is based on a proprietary methodology developed by ICONS to assess stakeholder engagement across communication channels.¹

The approach combines **outreach and engagement indicators** into composite engagement indices, enabling the analysis of Communication impacts for each area of activity. The three indices utilised are:

- Publication Engagement Index (PEI)

¹ Folco Giuliana, Gaboardi Elena, Lischetti Serena, Martinoli Mario, Mazzolo Giulio, & Schmid Elisabeth. (2022). Two new tools for science communication assessment: the community engagement index and communication effectiveness quadrants. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6985584>

- Website Engagement Index (WEI)
- Social Engagement Index (SEI)

The combined use of these indices results in the **Community Engagement Index (CEI)**, which integrates all communication activities into a single metric to evaluate the overall impact of a project.

To facilitate readability, the indices are normalised on a scale from 0 to 100, where the optimal value used for normalisation is defined based on more than 100 projects managed by ICONS. **The closer an index is to 100, the higher the level of engagement.**

The following paragraphs provide an overview of these indices and present the results of the monitoring activity up to 1 April 2026, when this report was drafted.

2.1.1 COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT INDEX (CEI)

The Community Engagement Index (CEI) offers a **comprehensive overview of SPOON's overall communication performance**. This single index combines all activity areas (social media, website and editorial publications) through a specific calculation designed to avoid double-counting across channels.

The table below presents the outreach and engagement data for each index and the associated score on a range from 0 to 100.

Table 1 Engagement indices

Index	Outreach	Engagement	Norm. (/100)
CEI	34,043	9,194	129
WEI	8,735	4,090	85
SEI	18,770	3,947	84
PEI	16,334	2,379	77

With a normalised score of 129/100, SPOON is performing significantly better than comparable projects in terms of overall engagement and **exceeds the optimal value**.

Figure 1 presents the CEI by impact area, showing which index plays a bigger role in the overall performance. In the SPOON case, **social media activities** generate the highest impact in terms of both outreach and engagement.

Figure 1 CEI by impact area

2.1.2 PUBLICATION ENGAGEMENT INDEX (PEI)

The Publication Engagement Index (PEI) evaluates the overall performance of **editorial content** published on the SPOON website and promoted through social media channels. This content includes press releases, news articles, project updates, newsletter issues and videos.

A total of **26 publications** have been produced since the beginning of the project. The publications consist of 9 news releases, 6 social media clips, 5 event releases, 3 press releases, 2 newsletters and 1 video. All materials are available at: <https://spoonproject.eu/all-news/#>. These formats generated **16,334 impressions**, including website page views, views on multiplier platforms, and impressions from related social media posts. Engagement reached **2,379 interactions**, including both social media interactions and downloads from multiplier platforms.

Once project activities began to develop in June 2025, editorial output maintained a **steady publishing rhythm**, with a slight increase over the past two months, ensuring a continuous stream of impactful content. As shown in Figure 2, outreach registered **two significant peaks** – in January 2025 and January 2026 – associated respectively with the press release announcing the launch of the project and the press release presenting the first iterations of the Citizen Science Labs. The high visibility achieved by these two pieces highlights the effectiveness of well-coordinated communication efforts that combine editorial production with multipliers and social media amplification.

Figure 2 Editorial output with outreach and engagement

Looking at the effectiveness of production in terms of engagement, **video content** generates the highest number of interactions. With 1,273 visualisations and 743 interactions, the project video is the content with the highest outreach and engagement. In terms of interactions, it is followed by:

- Video Pilot – Thessaloniki (210 interactions)
- Video Pilot – Braunschweig (169 interactions)
- Press release: *Putting citizens at the forefront of food system transformation* (163 interactions)
- Press release: *Citizens to help shape food research* (123 interactions)
- Video Pilot – Pomurje (114 interactions)

2.1.3 WEBSITE ENGAGEMENT INDEX (WEI)

By April 2026, the [SPOON website](#) had recorded a total of **4,382 visits**, lasting two minutes on average. Visitors come primarily from Italy (1,190), the United States (553), Germany (511), Spain (375) and Greece (337).

Figure 3 provides insight into **user behaviour**, showing how visitors accessed the website. Entry points are summarised as follows:

- 66% of visitors accessed the website directly
- 19% reached SPOON through search engines
- 9% entered the website through social media
- 6% arrived via referral links from external websites

Channel Types

Figure 3 Entry points

Overall, the website generated **8,735 pageviews**, of which **4,090 lasted longer than one minute**. These figures support the assessment of the Website Engagement Index (WEI), which combines outreach (total pageviews) and engagement (pageviews exceeding one minute). With a score of 85/100, the SPOON website demonstrates **good performance**, with greater expectations as to when the project will unfold its results. Based on pageviews, the most popular webpages are:

- Homepage: 3,427 pageviews
- What is SPOON: 800 pageviews
- SPOON pilots: 747 pageviews

Figure 4 shows that **three notable peaks** were registered across the reference period. These can be associated, respectively, with the website launch (July 2025), the iterations of the CSLs (October 2025), and the release of the pilot videos (March 2026).

Figure 4 Website engagement

The website also serves as the primary access point for documents, scientific publications, papers, and public deliverables. In total, the [Resources page](#) on the website recorded **810 downloads**, indicating strong interest in the project's outputs. The same resources have been downloaded an additional **628 times** directly on [Zenodo](#). The most downloaded resources are:

- Roll up (281 downloads)
- Leaflet (173 downloads)
- Brandbook (154 downloads)
- Project launch PR (60 downloads)
- D5.1 Evaluation Framework (28 downloads)

2.1.4 SOCIAL ENGAGEMENT INDEX (SEI)

The Social Engagement Index (SEI) evaluates the performance of the SPOON social media accounts on LinkedIn, Instagram, and YouTube. With **458 followers** and **155 published posts**, the accounts generated a total of **18,770 impressions** (views) and **3,947 engagement actions**, including clicks, likes, comments, and shares. These metrics reflect outreach and engagement levels, respectively, resulting in an overall SEI score of 84/100.

In terms of outreach, the most successful post was the project's **promotional video**, which generated 941 impressions. This post also achieved the highest level of engagement, with 546 interactions. The second social content that reached the higher level of impressions is the post announcing the release of the *Handbook for the implementation and replication of Citizen Science Labs and Behaviour Change Interventions*.

Engagement data show once again that **video content** is the most effective format for driving audience interactions. Consistent with these findings, and as illustrated in the engagement and outreach trend graph below (Figure 5), peaks in performance align with specific campaigns and content releases, particularly video content, which consistently generates higher levels of visibility and interaction.

Figure 5 Social media trend over time with outreach and engagement

2.1.5 CONCLUSIONS

The **Community Engagement Index (CEI)** score of 129/100 confirms that the overall Communication and Dissemination (C&D) strategy is effective and performs well above benchmark levels. The integrated performance across channels demonstrates clear strategic coherence between editorial content and social media amplification. Maintaining and further strengthening this integration should remain a priority.

With a **Publication Engagement Index (PEI)** score of 77/100, publication performance can be considered very strong. Video content has proven to generate the highest levels of engagement and will therefore be further prioritised to increase both views and interactions. In addition, multipliers have demonstrated significant value in extending outreach and will continue to be strategically leveraged.

Based on a **Website Engagement Index (WEI)** of 85/100, the website stands out as one of the project’s strongest communication assets. High levels of direct traffic indicate solid brand recognition, while sustained user engagement reflects the relevance and quality of the published content. An increase in website traffic is expected in the coming months, supported by the growth of the social media audience and active content sharing by project partners. As project results become available and new dissemination materials are published, a corresponding rise in downloads is also anticipated.

The **Social Engagement Index (SEI)** score of 84/100 confirms that social media is a key driver of project visibility and community engagement. Interaction levels are particularly strong when content is linked to project milestones and supported by multimedia formats, reinforcing the importance of timely and visually engaging communication.

3. DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION

3.1 OVERVIEW OF KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

Tables 2 and 3 present the **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** related to the project's communication and dissemination activities.

At the current stage of the project, dissemination-related outputs are not expected to be fully achieved as key results, solutions, and tools are still under development. As a result, **communication** KPIs show a more advanced level of progress, while **dissemination** indicators remain ongoing.

Dissemination activities are nevertheless already planned and will advance in line with the development of project deliverables and solutions, as illustrated in the Dissemination Plan (Table 4).

Table 2 Communication measures and KPIs

Specific measures	KPI	Status
Visual Identity	Logo, templates, brand book (M2)	Achieved
Communication Kit	1 leaflet, roll-up, project video (M8)	Achieved
Project website	80,000 page views (M24), providing main access to the SPOON Digital Platform	8,735 page views (M16)
Social media	1000 followers; >1 social media thematic campaign/year in each CSL and >1 at the EU level	458 followers; 1 thematic campaign in each CSL; 1 EU-level campaign
Press and news releases	10 by the end of the project, outreach of 1000s users	3 press releases 9 news releases
Journalistic articles	3 journalistic articles, outreach of 1000s users	First journalistic article: M18
Video interviews	6 short videos for social media, >600 views	6 vox pop videos: M20

Table 3 Dissemination KPIs

Specific measures	KPIs	Status
Scientific publications	>7 open access publications on highly ranked journals and ResearchGate	Publications plan in progress
Info-packs and Factsheets	>8 in total by the end of the project	Infopack #1 and #2: M20
Best Practices Book	1 Best Practices Book, >300 downloads	Planned
Video tutorial of the SPOON Digital Dashboard	1 video tutorial, >250 views	Planned
Podcast	4 episodes, >100 streams per episode	Topics, structure and timeline: M20
Policy Brief	1 policy brief with recommendations	Planned
Synergies with other projects & initiatives	>4 joint activities (events, webinars, campaigns, publications)	Planned
Events	>10 external events/fairs attended; >2 dissemination workshops at each CSL (30 part. Each), final event (>50 part.), 2 webinars for EU-wide dissemination (>50 part. each)	2 external events 1 workshop at each CSL

3.2 DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

3.2.1 DISSEMINATION PLAN

To maximise the visibility, adoption, and long-term impact of the **Key Exploitable Results** (KERs), a structured and targeted dissemination plan has been developed. This plan is presented in Table 4, which outlines each KER, its main topic, and the specific format used to communicate it. The chosen formats – infopacks, factsheets, policy brief, and best practice book – ensure that technical findings are translated into **accessible, audience-tailored materials**.

Compared to the initial Communication and Dissemination Plan, in which only a preliminary set of topics for factsheets and info-packs had been identified, this updated strategy further specifies the sources from which their content will be developed.

The timing of each dissemination activity will depend on the availability and maturity of project results, as well as on the submission schedule of the related deliverables. All dissemination outputs will be made available through Zenodo and linked to the project website. To maximise outreach and visibility, each output will be promoted through **news releases and social media posts**. Project partners will be promptly informed of new publications and encouraged to further disseminate them through their own networks and communication channels.

Table 4 Dissemination plan

KER	Title	Partner	Format	Target audience
KER 6	Handbook for implementation and replication of CSLs and BCIs	SFC	Info-pack #1	Local and regional authorities related to the food system; Civil society organisations and NGOs
KER 8	Insight in barriers for sharing personal data related to food	CSCP	Info-pack #2	Research and academic institutions; Civil society organisations and NGOs; Industry actors and SME
KER 1	Insight in factors affecting European sustainable and healthy food consumption across Europe.	EV ILVO	Info-pack #3	Local and regional authorities related to the food system; Research and academic institutions; Civil society organisations and NGOs;
KER 8	DIY manual for a successful implementation of CSLs in the food sector	CSCP	Info pack #4	Local and regional authorities related to the food system; Civil society organisations and NGOs
KER 2	Online database of best practices using CS in food system transformation	EV ILVO	Factsheet #5	Local and regional authorities related to the food system; Civil society organisations and NGOs
KER 3 KER 4 KER 5	SPOON digital toolset v2	JIBE	Info pack #6	Civil society organisations and NGOs; Industry actors and SME

KER 7	Report on results of 6 SPOON Citizen Science Labs/Report on results of the SPOON behaviour change interventions	CSCP	Best practice book	Local and regional authorities related to the food system; Civil society organisations and NGOs; Policymakers and public administrators; Citizens and communities
KER 11	SPOON Monitoring Toolkit v2	AIT	Info pack #7	Local and regional authorities related to the food system; Research and academic institutions; Civil society organisations and NGOs;
KER 9	'SPOON Academy' capacity-building programme	CSCP	Factsheet #8	Local and regional authorities related to the food system; Research and academic institutions; Civil society organisations and NGOs;
KER 10	Policy recommendations package	AIT	Policy brief	Policymakers and public administrators; Local and regional authorities related to the food system

3.3 COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

3.3.1 WEBSITE

Launched as a landing page in M2 (January 2025) and officially released in its full version in M8 (July 2025), the [SPOON website](#) (figure 6), serves as the central hub for communication and dissemination activities, hosting **project-related content**, including news, updates, events, public deliverables, publications and key results.

Figure 6 Homepage of SPOON's website

The website is structured into the following main sections:

- [What is SPOON](#)
- [How SPOON works](#)
- [Pilots](#)
- Insights (including [News](#), [Events](#) and [Resources](#))

Developed using WordPress, the website plays a key role in ensuring a simple, accessible and user-friendly experience for a broad audience. Its **accessibility** is enhanced through the use of clear, engaging language inspired by food-related metaphors, as well as the availability of pilot pages in both English and local languages ([German](#), [Greek](#), [Dutch](#), [Slovene](#), [Italian](#), [Spanish](#)), which have been developed following a targeted storytelling approach. These local-language sections also allow partners to publish news and events in their respective languages, helping them better reach and engage local audiences.

To ensure accurate and up-to-date website content, all partners are encouraged to actively support content development by keeping ICONS informed about relevant initiatives, developments, milestones, news and events.

The project adopted an **inclusive web design**, carefully selecting colours, typography, and navigation structures to minimise potential barriers linked to gender, age, or socio-economic background, thereby improving accessibility for a wide range of users.

Website – Updated strategy

In the coming months, the website will be regularly updated with new content, including project results, events and dissemination materials.

The website will host and provide access to key project outputs as they become available. In addition, the website will serve as the main entry point to the SPOON Digital Platform (WP2), once fully developed, ensuring easy access for users.

3.3.2 SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media is a core component of SPOON's communication and dissemination strategy, enabling the project to reach diverse audiences and activate the networks of partners and Citizen Science Labs (CSLs). The strategy combines continuous communication on project developments, key results and upcoming events with dedicated thematic campaigns

Profiles on **LinkedIn** and **Instagram** were created in M8 (July 2025), with content tailored to the specific audiences of each platform. Content production is ongoing and supported by the active involvement of consortium partners and CSL participants. To support CSLs in the creation of SPOON-related content with formats consistent with the project visual identity, they were provided with editable social media templates that can be easily adapted to communicate SPOON-related updates on partners' local channels.

A **YouTube channel** was also launched to support the dissemination of audiovisual materials, starting with the project presentation video. The channel will be further expanded with additional video materials, as described in more detail in Section 3.5.4 Video production.

In terms of **campaigns**, the first EU-level social media initiative, *What’s Behind SPOON*, was launched at the beginning of the project to introduce the project partners. A second campaign focused on the project pilots: one video was produced for each Citizen Science Lab (CSL) to present the local initiatives and increase their visibility.

Social Media – Updated strategy
<p>In the next phase, social media will place stronger emphasis on thematic campaigns and video content, with a clearer focus on the activities and results emerging from the CSLs.</p> <p>Campaigns, one per year, will be developed around key project moments and outputs, bringing CSL experiences to the forefront of communication and making them more visible and accessible to different audiences.</p> <p>Video content will play a central role, building on the material currently being produced within the CSLs, described in more detail in Section 3.5.4 – Video production, designed to capture experiences, perspectives, and results more directly and engagingly.</p>

3.3.3 NEWSLETTER

The project newsletter is issued **every six months** to keep subscribers informed about the latest developments and activities of the project. Each edition provides an overview of key milestones, upcoming events, project outputs, and relevant results.

All published editions are made accessible through the “News” section of the SPOON website. Content is gathered continuously from project partners, ensuring broad and up-to-date coverage of activities across the consortium.

Following each release, partners are encouraged to further expand its reach by sharing the newsletter through their own communication channels and stakeholder networks.

To date, two editions of the SPOON newsletter have been published and distributed to a total of **73 subscribers**.

Table 5 SPOON newsletter issues

	Date	Reached	Opens	Reactivity
SPOON Newsletter #2	24.03.2026	69	71%	46%

SPOON Newsletter #1	23.10.2025	56	75%	54%
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The data collected so far provide a first indication of the newsletter performance. As shown in the table above, the number of recipients has slightly grown, reflecting a gradual expansion of the subscriber base.

Open rates have remained relatively high, indicating effective targeting and the use of subject lines and sender recognition that encourage users to open the emails.

Reactivity, measured as the ratio between clicks and opens, remains around 50%, pointing to a good level of interaction with the content after opening the newsletter.

Newsletter – Updated strategy

Throughout the next phases of the project, four new newsletter editions will be published (approximately in M23, M29, M35, and M41), focusing on call-to-action strategy and content structure to increase reader interaction.

3.4 MATERIALS AND FORMATS

3.4.1 COMMUNICATION KIT AND OTHER MATERIALS

The SPOON communication kit was finalized in M8 to provide a set of resources for effectively communicating the project and ensuring a consistent visual identity across all activities.

The kit includes materials designed to support project presentation and outreach in events and meetings with external stakeholders. It comprises a **leaflet**, in English and local languages, a **roll-up banner**, a **master PowerPoint presentation**, and a **promotional project video** (see Section 3.5.4 – Video production for details).

In addition to these materials, further communication tools were developed to support engagement within the CSLs. These include **pilot-specific flyers** in local languages, providing contextual information about each pilot and featuring QR codes linking to the respective local landing pages. **Templates for customizable flyers** were also created, enabling CSLs to produce tailored content based on specific needs. Finally, a **set of stickers** was designed to enhance visibility and foster a recognizable project identity at the local level.

These materials are available in digital format on a dedicated [Zenodo page](#) accessible also via the [Resources](#) section of the project website.

Leaflet

The SPOON leaflet presents the project’s overall vision, objectives, and key elements supporting its implementation.

It is **available in English and in the local languages** of the pilot sites. The leaflet provides a concise overview of the cities involved and includes a QR code linking to the project website in the English version, and to the corresponding local landing pages in the translated versions.

The leaflet design has been conceived to immediately evoke the food dimension of the project: when folded along the lines dividing the different sections, it takes the shape of a bowl, reinforcing the project’s thematic focus and creating a more engaging and memorable user experience. Figure 7 presents the leaflet in folded and unfolded format.

Roll-up banner

SPOON also produced a roll-up in 200×85 cm format for **in-person events** (figure 8). It serves as a quick and engaging entry point for audiences, offering a concise **overview of the project**. The content includes the project title and mission, a QR code directing visitors to the SPOON website, and a visual reference to the six European pilot sites involved. Through this, the banner **supports outreach activities** by drawing attention and facilitating initial engagement with both stakeholders and the general public.

Figura 8 Leaflet, folded and unfolded

Figura 7 Roll-up

Power Point presentation

Partners use the SPOON **PowerPoint presentation** as a shared tool to communicate the project in a clear and coherent way across different contexts. The presentation brings together the main elements of the project, including its vision, objectives, overall approach, and an overview of the pilot activities.

It is primarily intended to **support presentations** delivered by consortium members, as well as interactions with stakeholders and broader dissemination efforts.

Stickers

Given the participatory and community-oriented nature of the project, **branded stickers** were also produced. Two versions are available and are distributed during events and local activities to increase visibility and engagement.

Figure 9 Stickers

Flyers

A series of **flyers** was developed in **local languages**, one for each CSL. The front side presents the pilot’s mission and includes a call-to-action inviting citizens to participate, along with a QR code linking to the local landing page. The back side highlights the connection with the SPOON project and provides additional project information.

To support local communication, **editable flyer templates** were also created, enabling CSLs to easily adapt content to their needs while maintaining a coherent visual identity. These templates can be used for **event promotion** or targeted **calls to action**.

Figure 10 Spanish flyer

Other contributions

In addition to the materials presented above, ICONS contributed to the design and visual development of other project outputs, including the **Food journal** (WP3), the **multimedia questionnaire** (WP2), and the **PowerPoint presentation for the SPOON digital dashboard** (WP2).

Communication kit & other materials – Updated strategy

In the next phase, efforts will focus on increasing the visibility, distribution, and use of the communication materials developed so far, both at EU level and across the CSLs.

Particular attention will be given to promoting access to the materials available on Zenodo and encouraging their use in events, meetings, and local activities.

WP7, as the work package dedicated to C&D activities, will remain responsive to emerging needs by supporting the development of additional communication materials if considered relevant, especially in relation to new tools and outputs that will be developed in the final phase of the project.

3.4.2 INFOPACKS AND FACTSHEETS

Factsheets and info-packs are concise, **synthetic reports** designed for the professional community, providing **technical insights** into the solutions, methodologies, and approaches developed within the project.

This format translates technical achievements and findings into content that is easier to explore and more engaging for a wider audience. Within the SPOON project, a total of 8 info-packs and/or factsheets will be produced. As anticipated in the Dissemination Plan (Table 4), the content will be primarily drawn from public deliverables issued within the project and other key project outputs.

These dissemination outputs will be available for download on the project website and shared with selected groups of key stakeholders.

Infopacks and Factsheets – Updated strategy

The first two infopacks, based on the deliverables submitted to date (D3.1 and D1.1), are planned for M20.

Further infopacks and factsheets will be progressively developed in alignment with the preparation of upcoming deliverables, ensuring consistency with the dissemination plan outlined in Table 4.

3.4.3 EIP-AGRI PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

Practice Abstracts follow the format defined by the European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) for communicating project activities, results, and practical knowledge. This format is designed to **facilitate knowledge exchange** on innovative and practice-oriented projects throughout their lifecycle, enabling farmers, advisors, researchers, and other actors across the EU to access relevant insights and connect with one another.

SPOON will produce a total of six abstracts, aiming to **deliver key findings** to practitioners and stakeholders in the agri-food sector. The first batch of three Practice Abstracts was published on the [EU CAP Network platform](#) in M16 (March 2026), with the following content:

1. Citizen Science Labs: engaging citizens to transform food systems
2. Overcoming barriers to sharing food-related personal data: practical insights for practitioners
3. Guidelines for the implementation and replication of Citizen Science Labs

EIP-AGRI Practice Abstracts – Updated strategy

As part of the updated communication and dissemination strategy, D7.3 (Practice Abstracts – Group 1) will be submitted in M18. Its content will then be further developed into a dedicated dissemination product to maximise its visibility and impact. Design, publication on Zenodo, and promotion through SPOON's communication channels will take place between M19 and M21.

The preparation of a second batch of Practice Abstracts will begin, with three additional abstracts planned for release at M48, focusing on the following topics: 1) the role of citizen-generated food data in the agri-food value chain transformation, 2) barriers and drivers for sustainable and healthy food consumption, 3) Citizen Science Academy: replicating CSL and BCI learnings.

3.4.4 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

The project is expected to produce scientific results of significant relevance, suitable for dissemination at international conferences and for publication in open-access journals.

A total of **seven scientific papers** will highlight the project's most significant and innovative outcomes. These publications will be led by the technical partners, while updates on the release of SPOON's peer-reviewed outputs will be communicated through the project's official website and social media channels.

Scientific publications – Updated strategy

A structured publications plan will be developed to support the project’s scientific dissemination activities. The plan will identify potential publication topics, define a preliminary timeline, and outline the partners responsible for each contribution. It will also explore opportunities for internal collaboration within the consortium, fostering joint publications and maximising the scientific impact of the project.

3.4.5 POLICY BRIEFS, BEST PRACTICE BOOK, VIDEO TUTORIAL

Key project results and experiences will be compiled into a final publication: the **Best Practice Book**. This publication will **present the main achievements and innovations** of the project in a structured and visually engaging format, showcasing how the project’s approaches and solutions have been implemented in practice.

The Best Practice Book will draw on the outcomes generated throughout the project, including the results of the Citizen Science Labs and other relevant project deliverables. In particular, it will build on findings presented in key outputs such as **D4.1**, Report on results of 6 SPOON Citizen Science Labs, and **D4.2**, Report on results of the SPOON behaviour change interventions, translating these results into a format that is accessible to a broader audience beyond the project’s technical community.

Designed as a compact but comprehensive overview of the project’s outcomes, the publication will highlight practical insights, **lessons learned and transferable practices** that can support replication and uptake beyond the project’s lifetime. The Best Practice Book will be developed in collaboration with the relevant technical partners and will be made available for download on the project website.

In addition, a **policy brief** will be prepared to communicate key policy-relevant findings and recommendations to policymakers and public authorities. The document will build on the results presented in deliverable D6.5 “Policy recommendations package” (M48), translating these recommendations into a concise and accessible format tailored to policy audiences and highlighting how Citizen Science approaches can support the transformation of food systems.

Finally, a **video tutorial** will be produced to **promote the project’s digital dashboard**, illustrating its main functionalities, benefits for end-users and overall user-friendliness. The content of the video will be defined in collaboration with the relevant technical partners, while ICONS will be responsible for its production and dissemination through the project website and social media channels.

3.5 EDITORIAL FORMATS

3.5.1 NEWS AND PRESS RELEASES

Regular updates on the project’s progress are delivered through **news items** and **press releases**, which cover activities, results, publications, and key technical outputs. These

communication outputs contribute to keeping stakeholders informed while supporting **transparency** and broader **awareness** at both the European and local levels.

The dissemination process combines central coordination and partner contributions. Content is first published on the project website and then circulated via social media and the project newsletter. Partners support this process by providing timely inputs on relevant developments, results, publications, and events, which are turned into communication materials. Once available, these outputs are further shared through partners' own channels and local media, helping to extend their reach and reinforce engagement, particularly within local contexts.

At this stage, **20 editorial items** have been produced, including press releases, news items, event-related content, and newsletters. This means that the initial target of 10 news and press releases set for the entire project has already been met.

News and Press releases – Updated strategy

The production of news and press releases will continue throughout the project to ensure regular communication of ongoing activities and results, while supporting the project's visibility and engagement with stakeholders.

3.5.2 JOURNALISTIC ARTICLES

Journalistic articles help extend the project's communication beyond its core stakeholders, reaching a broader, non-specialist audience. Written by **professional journalists**, they present the project's activities and results in a clear and engaging way.

By placing the project within a wider socio-economic and environmental context, they raise awareness of the issues addressed and contribute to greater media visibility. SPOON will release a total of three journalistic articles, which will be published on the project website, promoted through the project's social media channels, and further amplified through European and **international media multipliers** - such as [Youris](#), [EU Agenda](#) and [AlphaGalileo](#) - to maximise visibility.

The first journalistic article will be published **by the end of May 2026**.

Journalistic Articles – Updated strategy

Two additional journalistic articles are foreseen for the second half of the project. In preparation, brainstorming activities will be carried out in the coming months to identify relevant and engaging topics aligned with the project's objectives and target audiences.

3.5.3 PODCAST EPISODES

Four podcast episodes are planned over the course of the project. Where relevant, project's partners may be invited as guests, contributing to the podcast content while also fostering their engagement and continued involvement.

The content, format, and production approach will be defined progressively, in collaboration with project partners, ensuring alignment with ongoing activities and opportunities for dissemination. Where relevant and appropriate, potential collaborations with sister projects and existing podcast channels may also be explored. Episodes will be hosted in the [ICONS Innovation Stories Spotify channel](#) and shared through the project's communication channels.

Podcast – Updated strategy

The planning of the podcast series, including the definition of topics, structure, and timeline, is scheduled for M20.

3.5.4 VIDEO PRODUCTION

Video production represents a key strategic communication tool for the project, supporting the promotion of SPOON, the **visibility** of the pilot sites, and the ongoing **engagement** of a broad audience of citizens.

To date, the project has produced a series of video materials, including the **promotional video** and **six short videos** showcasing each pilot site, developed with the contribution of CSL coordinators. Overall, these videos have reached a total of **984 views** across the project's communication channels.

Video production – Updated strategy

Six additional vox-pop videos (one per pilot) will be produced, based on interviews conducted by CSL coordinators during meetings with citizens scheduled for M18–19. These videos will focus on the following themes: defining healthy and sustainable meals, changing food behaviours, and perceptions of the project. The videos will then be edited and published between M21 and M22.

4 CLUSTERING, SYNERGIES AND EVENTS

4.1 CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES

As part of Task 7.4, SPOON has initiated a structured **mapping of EU-funded and relevant national/regional initiatives** working on topics aligned with SPOON (see Annex 2). This mapping is intended as a living resource to support the clustering approach described in this plan and to prioritise collaboration opportunities based on thematic alignment, complementarity of activities, and potential for joint communication, mutual learning and/or shared stakeholder engagement.

In the first stage, SPOON prioritised projects that are in closer link to the consortium due to existing internal connections, such as shared partners, established contacts through previous collaborations, or clear overlaps in methods (e.g., living labs / citizen science approaches), data-related workstreams, and policy engagement. For each of these projects, summarised in the table provided in Annex 2, SPOON has preliminarily assessed the **clustering potential** (e.g., knowledge exchange, joint dissemination, joint workshops, alignment on data and citizen-generated evidence, policy uptake channels) and has initiated first exchanges /outreach to open a dialogue and explore concrete synergies.

In parallel, other mapped initiatives are kept “on the radar” to be invited to relevant clustering moments and joint activities as they are developed over the course of the project. These initiatives involve: Data4Food2030, FOODITY, DRG4Food, FNS-Cloud, S3FOOD, PROTEIN, F2F Health Matters, CLEVERFOOD, ECS, INCREASE, FEAST, FOODCLIC, OBAMA-NEXT, RefreSCAR, EUTOPIA_HEALTH, ERA4Health, CHOICE, FOODCoST, PLANEAT, SWITCH, REACT, ENHANCE, BETTER-B, GES4SEAS, PlasticUnderground.

4.2 COLLABORATION PLAN

4.2.1 COLLABORATION WITH SISTER PROJECT FOOD MISSION

SPOON has initiated bilateral exchanges with the sister project FOODMISSION to explore concrete clustering opportunities and identify areas of complementarity. These first conversations have focused on aligning approaches to citizen engagement, citizen-generated data, and behaviour change, and on identifying opportunities for joint learning and coordinated outreach.

FOODMISSION is setting up **Transformation Labs (T-Labs)** as multi-actor spaces supporting the project from co-design to uptake, alongside the development of a citizen science data framework and a gamified educational virtual platform piloted in multiple European countries. This makes FOODMISSION particularly relevant for **methodological exchange** with SPOON’s

CSL model, and for joint reflection on engagement and retention strategies (including digital and gamified approaches).

Collaboration with FOODMISSION is being structured around two main tracks:

1. Mutual learning between SPOON CSLs and FOODMISSION T-Labs

A targeted mutual learning exercise will be developed to compare and exchange practical lessons across lab formats (CSLs vs. T-Labs), including:

- stakeholder recruitment and engagement strategies;
- co-creation and facilitation methods;
- approaches to sustaining participation over time (including FOODMISSION's gamification elements);
- approaches to collecting, managing and reusing citizen-generated data for policy and practice.

2. Joint contribution to the Task 7.4 clustering milestone at M24

Building on the ongoing exchanges, SPOON and FOODMISSION are exploring possibilities to co-shape / contribute to the Task 7.4 workshop foreseen at Month 24, including options such as:

- a joint session showcasing and comparing early lab implementation experiences (CSLs and T-Labs);
- peer feedback on lab protocols and engagement tools;
- identification of shared messages and early results relevant for policy and stakeholder communities.

Collaboration with sister project FOOD Mission – Updated strategy

1. Bilateral coordination exchanges (ongoing): scoping discussions to map areas of synergy and identify focal points in each project for clustering follow-up.
2. CSL–T-Lab mutual learning exercise (to be scheduled): short series of exchanges among lab coordinators (online), potentially complemented by targeted participation as observers in selected lab sessions where feasible.
3. M24 workshop preparation (in progress): definition of how FOODMISSION can be involved (e.g., joint agenda item, shared session, invited contributions), aligned with the maturity of each project's early implementation.
4. Coordination on dissemination (as opportunities arise): cross-promotion of relevant public outputs, news, and participation calls, and identification of opportunities for joint positioning within wider Food Systems / Citizen Science communities.

4.2.2 STRATEGIC COOPERATION WITH THE JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE & OTHER SUPPORT MEASURES

To enhance **scientific validity and policy impact**, SPOON will establish strategic cooperation with the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre (JRC). This collaboration will build on SPOON’s citizen science approach and its focus on food security and behavioural change.

SPOON already identified relevant JRC services, in particular:

- Citizen Science team involved in [EU Citizen Science for Policy initiatives](#)
- Units contributing to the [Knowledge Centre for Food and Nutrition Security](#)
- Services connected to [Knowledge for Policy \(K4P\)](#) platforms.

The cooperation with JRC will focus on **ongoing and upcoming SPOON activities**, following a phased approach aligned with the project timeline (M14–M48) and the progressive maturity of results.

1. **Citizen science methodologies and data governance (early–mid phase | WP2, WP3, WP4)** - *Indicative timeframe: M14–M30*
 - Alignment of SPOON’s citizen science methodologies and data governance approach with JRC citizen science frameworks and standards, during the active implementation of CSLs.
 - Exchange on the design, quality and reuse of citizen-generated data for policy-relevant purposes, building on JRC experience from initiatives such as [EU-Citizen.Science](#), [CitizenSData](#), DigiTranScope, and related COST Actions.
 - Reflection on interoperability, ethical use and long-term usability of citizen science data produced within SPOON.
2. **Validation and impact assessment of SPOON results (mid phase | WP5)** - *Indicative timeframe: M24–M40*
 - Targeted engagement with JRC experts to support the **scientific validation** of SPOON tools, methodologies and datasets as they mature.
 - Contributions to impact evaluation and monitoring activities under WP5, including:
 - Scientific assessment of the SPOON toolset (T5.4);
 - Validation of robustness, innovation potential and scalability of Behaviour Change Interventions (BCIs) emerging from the CSLs.
 - Exchange on indicators, metrics and evaluation frameworks relevant for citizen science-based food system interventions.
3. **Policy uptake, exploitation and scaling pathways (late phase | WP6)** - *Indicative timeframe: M36–M48*
 - Sharing consolidated SPOON findings on food security, behavioural change and citizen engagement through JRC Knowledge for Policy (K4P) platforms and related channels.
 - Dialogue on how SPOON evidence and methodologies can inform policy processes at EU and national level.

- Use of JRC insights to strengthen SPOON's exploitation, replication and post-project impact strategy, particularly regarding the scaling of citizen science initiatives and tools.

Finally, the project will leverage other horizontal support measures:

- [Horizon Results Booster](#) will be used to support the definition of a joint dissemination strategy portfolio with similar EU-funded projects.
- Existing initiatives, events, and channels (e.g. EC Mutual Learning Exercise on Citizen Science Initiatives, Food 2030 pathways) will be leveraged to maximise visibility and cross-fertilisation.

Strategic cooperation with the JRC - Updated strategy

Planned activities

- Planned activities will be defined progressively, in line with the maturity of SPOON results and mutual interest with JRC, and may evolve over the course of the project.
- Regular exchanges to define detailed content, timeline, and modalities of cooperation.
- Potentially suggest hosting two expert workshops:
 - Workshop 1 (M24): Presentation of SPOON scientific results.
 - Workshop 2 (M46): Presentation of CSL and BCI outcomes.

Implementation

- CSCP has proposed additional ideas for engagement with JRC. These contributions will be further elaborated jointly within the WP7 partners to refine this action.
- PNO leads and coordinates the interactions with JRC, in line with the scope, areas of cooperation and phased approach described above.
- The proposed cooperation strategy will be presented to the consortium in M27, with the aim of engaging relevant partners on a voluntary basis as topic-specific experts, depending on the themes under discussion and the maturity of SPOON results.

4.3 EVENTS

SPOON partners are requested to participate in relevant EU and local events to **raise the project's visibility** and sustain networking and clustering activities.

Partners are responsible for continuously tracking and reporting their communication and dissemination (C&D) activities, including participation in networking and clustering events, using the templates provided by ICONS. These templates should be regularly updated as activities take place. In addition, partners are requested to inform ICONS of any upcoming events they plan to attend on behalf of SPOON, in order to enable timely promotion and

visibility. Examples of relevant events include conferences, fairs, and workshops. Participation in these events is featured on the Project Website and on Social Media Channels to ensure the project's visibility.

Beyond the local events linked to SPOON's CSLs, such as workshops (e.g. [first experimental activities to introduce the project](#), [local workshop in Bruges](#)), conferences (e.g. [Climate conference in Braunschweig](#)) and clustering activities (e.g. [Transformation Lab with Foodmission](#)), as of M18 (May 2026), SPOON has been represented at two key international events: the [International Sustainability Transitions Conference \(IST 2025\)](#) in Lisbon, Portugal, and the [Smart City Expo World Conference \(SCEWC 2025\)](#), in Barcelona, Spain, contributing to increasing the project's visibility and engagement with relevant stakeholders.

Events – Updated strategy

SPOON will continue to engage in relevant networking and clustering opportunities to strengthen its visibility within the stakeholder community. Relevant international events and conferences will be mapped and monitored to support and encourage partners' participation. The following list anticipates some of the events that are considered relevant for clustering and dissemination purposes:

- **Food 4 Future / Expo FoodTech** – flagship FoodTech congress + industry fair (automation, digitalisation, sustainability).
- **Sustainable Foods Summit, European edition** – sustainability impacts, sourcing, biodiversity; good for policy-adjacent dissemination and cross-project visibility.
- **Free From & Premium Food** – “free-from”, plant-based and premium products; useful for behavioural change / consumer trends connections.
- **EFFoST International Conference 2026** – academic + industry conference on resilient/sustainable food systems; good for research dissemination and clustering with scientific initiatives.

Partners will notify upcoming events, which are monitored through internal communication flows and biannual data collection by ICONS. Priority will be given to conferences, fairs, and workshops aligned with the project's scope, where communication materials can be distributed.

5. LOCAL C&D ACTIVITIES

5.1 LOCAL DESKS: ROLE AND RESPONSIBILITIES

Within SPOON, Local Desks act as **key coordination hubs for communication activities** across the six pilots, ensuring a coherent and consistent implementation of the strategy at the local level. They serve as main link between ICONS, in its role as the project's Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Secretariat, and local contexts, bridging the gap with the specific social, cultural, and geographical characteristics of each site.

While the ICONS is responsible for defining and coordinating SPOON's overall communication strategy, Local Desks adapt and implement it locally.

In particular, each Local Desk is expected to:

- Provide **locally generated content** and insights to the C&D Secretariat for dissemination at the EU level
- **Share SPOON-related information** and materials within local communities
- Coordinate and support engagement activities involving citizens, organisations, and policymakers
- **Monitor and report** on local C&D actions, including events, workshops, and outreach initiatives
- Ensure alignment with the actions defined in the local C&D Plan
- **Promote visibility** and media coverage of project activities and results at the local level
- Disseminate project content through local digital and social media channels

Through these activities, Local Desks contribute to ensuring that SPOON's communication and dissemination efforts remain coherent, inclusive, and responsive to local contexts, strengthening the link between European objectives and **community-level action**.

5.2 LOCAL C&D PLANS

CSLs coordinators developed Local Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Plans, following a common structure and methodology provided by ICONS. While this shared framework ensures coherence and alignment with SPOON's overarching C&D strategy, each Local Plan is **tailored to the specific socio-cultural and geographical context**.

Their purpose is to make SPOON's messages meaningful and relevant to local audiences, while also capturing insights, stories, and results from the ground to enrich the project's wider communication efforts.

Each Local Plan (see Annex 1) includes a description of the objectives and the approach adopted, as well as an overview of key messages, local target audiences, and the online and offline communication channels to be used.

Through this approach, Local Desks act as SPOON's ambassadors, promoting visibility, engagement, and participation among citizens, organisations, and local decision-makers. By aligning local actions with the overarching SPOON C&D strategy, the Local Plans ensure **consistency, enhance impact**, and contribute to building an **active community of practice** that strengthens the project's long-term communication outcomes across Europe.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This updated Communication and Dissemination Plan is effective immediately and will guide SPOON's activities in the coming months, with a focus on its structured implementation and the continuous monitoring of its performance against the defined objectives.

All partners are expected to actively contribute to the promotion of the project and the dissemination of its results, ensuring a coordinated and consistent effort across the consortium. This collective engagement will be key to maximising the project's visibility, outreach, and overall impact.

ANNEX 1 – C&D LOCAL PLANS

TURIN

1. LOCAL OBJECTIVES AND APPROACH

Each pilot builds on SPOON's mission to make food systems fairer, healthier, and more sustainable. This section highlights the **local goals** and the **participatory approaches** that guide the Lab's work, from citizen engagement and data collection to co-creation activities connecting science with daily life.

The Citizen Science Lab in Turin (**SpoonTO**) focuses on exploring and communicating the following themes:

- Enhance **citizens' awareness** of healthy and sustainable eating habits;
- Highlight the economic and social factors contributing to **food insecurity** in Turin;
- Promote behaviours that help **reduce food waste** and foster collective actions toward more sustainable practices;
- Address and **reduce the social stigma** towards food distribution initiatives and beneficiaries, affirming the value of dignity and food quality for all;

The Italian CSL (SpoonTO) will adopt a participatory approach based on Citizen Science and Living Lab principles. Activities will combine **co-creation workshops**, qualitative and quantitative **data collection**, and practical small-scale actions on food-related behaviours. In collaboration with the Torino Solidale Network, the CSL will actively involve both distribution stakeholders and food-aid beneficiaries. Through interactive sessions, shared analysis, and dissemination moments, the CSL will facilitate a **dialogue among citizens, researchers, and social actors**, generating evidence useful for the city and for SPOON. Additionally, SpoonTO intends to present and showcase the activities and themes addressed by SPOON at major food-related events that will be held in Turin to reach wider audiences and stimulate wider public engagement.

2. KEY MESSAGES

Key messages express the essence of what each pilot aims to communicate, the core ideas that reflect its purpose within the broader SPOON framework. They should be short, clear, and memorable, capturing the spirit of the local initiative. These messages distill the pilot's goals and values into a few key statements that can guide communication across all channels.

Beyond clarity, they should also serve as anchors for a **storytelling approach rooted in the local context**: narratives that reflect the specific culture, needs, and voices of each community. Framing communication through locally grounded stories helps make SPOON's broader objectives tangible and relatable, turning abstract concepts into experiences people can identify with and share.

To convey uniform messages and reach a wider audience at the city level, communication around Spoon and SpoonTO will be developed jointly by Rete CdQ and the City's EU Projects and Communication Unit. This will be based on a shared work plan and structured links between the two entities' communication channels. The aim is to establish **two-way communication**, disseminating SpoonTO to the local context while simultaneously gathering input from the local environment to enrich CSL research activities.

Table 1 Key messages

Local Key Messages
1. Eat the right food and give the food the right value
2. Shopping list ready, local groceries, nourishing food
3. Taste at your table: experiment, save, transform, and organize!
4. Zero Waste: Recycle, Reinvent, Re-enjoy
5. Do your part: share and inspire the change!

3. LOCAL TARGETS

SPOON thrives on diversity across cities and communities. Here, each CSL defines who to reach and involve — citizens, schools, businesses, local organisations, or policymakers — describing the **audiences that are most relevant** to its goals and context.

Table 2 Stakeholders

Category	Specific Organisation
General public	8 Case del Quartiere (community centers)
	9 non-profit organizations of Rete Torino Solidale distinct from Case del Quartiere (ACLI Torino, Arci Associazione Edera, Arci Spazio Giovani Alkadia, Consulta per le Persone in Difficoltà, Associazione Damamar, Sermig Arsenale della Pace, Associazione Gruppo Abele, Società Asili Notturni, UISP Centro polisportivo Massari)
	Associations member of Pun.to al Cibo informal network
	Signatories of the Food Atlas Protocol (Università di Torino, Politecnico di Torino, Università di Scienze Gastronomiche, Camera di Commercio di Torino, Città di Torino, Città Metropolitana, Ires Piemonte, Urban Lab e Regione Piemonte)

Young people (+ 18) / University students / Young civil volunteers (18-28 years)	Public and Private Universities: Università degli studi di Torino, Politecnico di Torino, Università Scienze Gastronomiche di Pollenzo High schools City of Turin and no profit organizations that have young volunteers in their staff (young people in Universal Civil Service in the City of Turin)
Local authorities	Department of Social Services of the City of Turin GIPA - Gruppo Interdipartimentale delle Politiche Alimentari (Interdepartmental Group for Food Policy within the City) Piedmont Region Metropolitan City of Turin
Research Centres	Public and Private Universities: Università degli studi di Torino, Politecnico di Torino, Università Scienze Gastronomiche di Pollenzo Food Atlas Scientific Network
Food Producers, Processors and Manufacturers	Companies that manage school canteens in Turin: CAMST Soc. Coop. a r.l., Euroristorazione s.r.l., Ladisa s.r.l., Vivenda s.p.a. Local SMEs engaged in past projects and aware/active in solidarity/food-waste prevention activities: Panacea social farm, UpToFarm, L'Alveare che dice sì, Biova Project
Retailers & HoReCa Sector	Novacoop, Coop or Esselunga

4. ONLINE & OFFLINE CHANNELS

This section presents how the CSL in Turin plans to engage its audiences through offline channels, such as **local events, collaborations, and campaigns**, and **online channels** - social media, websites, and newsletters.

Table 3 Online Strategy

Channel	Specific Channel	Formats	Target
Website	Rete delle Case del Quartiere	Introductory text to present SPOON and its activities; Invitations of each CSL meeting;	General public.

	website (dedicated project page)	Articles in collaboration with experts to get insights on the topic of food and food management in Turin, or articles recommended by the knowledge brokers	People who visit the Rete delle Case del Quartiere website to find out what we do in general and what projects we have going on.
Social media	Instagram	Post after each CSL meeting, tagging the City of Turin and Spoon's official profile. Post about the CSL methodology (Citizen Science and Living Lab approach). Reposting articles by partners/researchers involved in the SPOON project. Short reels (VOX POP videos)	General public Young people (+18)
Social media	LinkedIn	Institutional posts created by the City of Turin profile in collaboration with the Rete delle Case del Quartiere profile. Reposting articles by partners/researchers involved in the SPOON project	General public, local authorities, research centers, third sector organizations. Entities that are already known or new. They can be individual users or organizations.
Social Media	Facebook	Post after each CSL meeting. Reposting articles by partners/researchers involved in the SPOON project	General public.
Newsletter	Mail	Section that covers the project's progress, the work that has been done, and the events at which SpoonTO will be present for promotional purposes. Released every 2 months.	General public.
Press release		For specific events, when agreed with the City of Turin, press releases will be drafted in collaboration with the City of Turin (not ordinary channel)	Journalists

Table 4 Offline Strategy

Action	Specification
Events	<p>Participation or promotional stand at big food festival/events: Terra Madre- Salone del Gusto (24-27 September 2026), Giornata Mondiale dell'alimentazione (16 October 2026), events sponsored by the City of Turin.</p> <p>Participations at meetings and informal networks (e.g. “Il martedì del cibo”), Pun.to al cibo network, Food Atlas (coordinated by the University of Turin).</p> <p>Participation in events and projects related to food-related topics (i.e. CO-SUSTAIN), entertainment community events (feste di quartiere) (feste) or neighbors' annual festival (festa dei vicini) in city neighborhoods, particularly those where neighbourhood houses are located</p>
Distribution of materials	Roll-up, branded gadgets (stickers), QR code for online project content, informative flyers and leaflet
Use of digital materials during events	PPT or Canva presentation

BRAUNSCHWEIG

1. LOCAL OBJECTIVES AND APPROACH

Each pilot builds on SPOON’s mission to make food systems fairer, healthier, and more sustainable. This section highlights the **local goals** and the participatory approaches that guide the Lab’s work — from citizen engagement and data collection to co-creation activities connecting science with daily life.

The overarching goal of the CSL Braunschweig is to **improve access to fresh, local food while reducing food waste**, particularly at the household level. It addresses key challenges such as limited access to affordable fresh food, weak interaction between consumers and producers, and low appreciation of sustainable food systems. The pilot aims to strengthen local connections through community-based initiatives and to actively engage citizens and food actors. A central objective is to sensitise and empower citizens with the knowledge and tools needed to reduce food waste in private households and to initiate lasting behavioural change.

To achieve these goals, the pilot follows a **participatory, transdisciplinary approach rooted**

in local networks and development initiatives. Citizens and food actors are actively involved, with a particular focus on lower-middle-income groups. The citizen science methodology at the Institute of Design Studies of the Braunschweig University of Arts brings together art, design, and social sciences to explore alternative futures and foster dialogue between science, practice, and everyday life. Creative formats—ranging from visual arts to performative practices—serve both as tools for raising awareness and for collecting qualitative and quantitative data on food waste and everyday food practices.

2. KEY MESSAGES

Key messages express the **essence of what each pilot aims to communicate**, the core ideas that reflect its purpose within the broader SPOON framework. They should be short, clear, and memorable, capturing the **spirit of the local initiative**. These messages distill the pilot’s goals and values into a few key statements that can guide communication across all channels.

Beyond clarity, they should also serve as anchors for a **storytelling approach rooted in the local context**: narratives that reflect the specific culture, needs, and voices of each community. Framing communication through locally grounded stories helps make SPOON’s broader objectives tangible and relatable, turning abstract concepts into experiences people can identify with and share.

The communication strategy of the Braunschweig SPOON Pilot builds on local networks and uses visual approaches to make everyday food practices and sustainability challenges tangible. As a design studies institute, we draw on **interdisciplinary collaboration**—working with local food-related NGOs, research centers, and neighbourhood initiatives—to address complex societal problems. Citizen participation is central: we engage these communities directly to co-create solutions and generate knowledge. **Using images, creative formats, and participatory visual methods**, we make the topic of **food waste** and sustainable food accessible, relatable, and engaging.

Table 1 Key messages

Local Key Messages
1. Valuing food from farm to fork builds the foundation for a sustainable tomorrow
2. Reducing food waste starts at home — empowered citizens can make a difference
3. Transforming food systems begins with creative thinking—and bold common action
4. Local impact grows through connected actors—bridging disciplines and communities

3. LOCAL TARGETS

SPOON thrives on diversity across cities and communities. Here, each CSL defines who to reach and involve — citizens, schools, businesses, local organisations, or policymakers — describing the **audiences that are most relevant** to its goals and context.

Table 2 Stakeholders

Category	Specific Organisation
General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Neighbourhood organisation: St Magni Kirchengemeinde, DRK Kaufbar
Old People	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Senior Services Office of the City Council: Seniorenbüro Senior Citizens' Editorial Teams: Seniorenredaktion Radio Okerwelle
Young People	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Our HBK students (University of Fine Arts)
Vulnerable people/minorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women's association empowering women with migration backgrounds: FrauenBUNT Migration advisory service: Refugium Association for the local Ukrainian Community: Freie Ukraine
Local authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Several departments of the City Council > social affairs, environment, economy, agriculture, waste management
Research Centres	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thünen Institut (German Federal Institute for Research on Rural Areas, Forestry and Fisheries) Julius Kühn Institut 3 different Universities (TU Braunschweig, HBK, Ostfalia)
Food Producers, Processors and Manufacturers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organic Farm & Delivery Services: BioMobil, Hof Morgentau Farmers associations: Verband der Landfrauen
Retailers & HoReCa Sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cafés which are specially engaged in local & sustainable food: Café Lüttes, Café Bruns, Kaffeehaus Supermarkets: Alnatura
Third sector / Community initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Association against foodwaste: Foodsharing Local food council: Ernährungsrat Braunschweig Sustainability Center: Nachhaltigkeitszentrum

4. ONLINE & OFFLINE CHANNELS

This section presents how the CSL in Braunschweig plans to engage its audiences through offline channels, such as **local events, collaborations, and campaigns**, and **online channels** - social media, websites, and newsletters.

Table 3 Online Strategy

Channel	Specific Channel	Formats	Target
Website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HBK website • Online Event-Calendars: City Council, Network “Forschungsregion Braunschweig” 	Website news, Press Releases, event promotion	General Public & academia
Social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HBK Instagram Account • Sharing via Instagram Account from partners (Foodsharing, Ernährungsrat, Cafés...) 	Social media campaigns, video posting, events promotion	General Public
Newsletter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HBK newsletter • several partner’s newsletter (Nachhaltigkeitszentrum etc) 	News in existing newsletter	General Public
Media multipliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Braunschweiger Zeitung • Radio Okerwelle 	Dissemination of press releases, journalistic articles	General Public
Direct mailings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination of relevant content to stakeholders, academia and interested citizens 	Event promotion, reporting of the CSL methodology & activities, dissemination of relevant deliverables	Stakeholder and partners
Intranet/Community platforms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intranet of the research institute “JKI” • Eventlist of the Foodsharing Platform 	Event promotion	Stakeholder and partners

Table 4 Offline Strategy

Action	Specification
Events	Participation in local conferences, citizen engagement activities, common events with other cultural institutions (theatre & museum)
Distribution of materials	Project flyer & Leaflet, Stickers, Roll Up
Use of digital materials during events	Project ppt presentation, project presentation video and pilot videos
Other media/activities	Local newspapers and radio

BRUGES

1. LOCAL OBJECTIVES AND APPROACH

Each pilot builds on SPOON's mission to make food systems fairer, healthier, and more sustainable. This section highlights the **local goals** and the participatory approaches that guide the Lab's work — from citizen engagement and data collection to co-creation activities connecting science with daily life.

The Bruges pilot aims to **improve food literacy** and **empower citizens to make healthier and more sustainable food choices**, especially in neighbourhoods where unhealthy options are common and local collaboration is still developing. The final goal is to **increase knowledge of sustainable diets, strengthen local food networks** through the Bruges Food Lab, and **encourage behaviour changes** that support fairer and healthier food environments.

Activities will focus on **nutrition awareness, sustainability, community engagement, and collaborative planning**. Using a participatory, citizen science approach, residents will help collect data, co-design initiatives, and test small behaviour changes. Through workshops, surveys, and local collaboration, citizens will contribute to knowledge creation and develop solutions tailored to Bruges' specific food context.

2. KEY MESSAGES

Key messages express the **essence of what each pilot aims to communicate**, the core ideas that reflect its purpose within the broader SPOON framework. They should be short, clear, and memorable, capturing the **spirit of the local initiative**. These messages distill the pilot's goals and values into a few key statements that can guide communication across all channels.

Beyond clarity, they should also serve as anchors for a **storytelling approach rooted in the local context**: narratives that reflect the specific culture, needs, and voices of each

community. Framing communication through locally grounded stories helps make SPOON's broader objectives tangible and relatable, turning abstract concepts into experiences people can identify with and share.

The Bruges pilot speaks directly to neighbourhoods, starting from everyday food realities that people recognise: where they shop, what they eat, and what choices feel easy or difficult. **Communication is rooted in local stories** from residents, volunteers, and neighbourhood centres, using food as a shared language to open conversations about health, sustainability, and fairness. Storytelling highlights small moments and practical experiences: cooking together, mapping food options and trying something new. These practical experiences show that change is possible at a human scale. By making learning social, playful, and locally grounded, SPOON invites neighbourhoods to explore their food environment together and imagine healthier, more sustainable futures that feel achievable and shared.

Table 1 Key messages

Local Key Messages
1. Our neighbourhood shapes what we eat - together we can improve it.
2. Small food choices, made every day, can make a big difference for our health and planet.
3. Everyone's experience matters: your food habits are valuable knowledge.
4. By sharing food stories and data, we learn what works in <i>our</i> neighbourhood.
5. Working together around food helps build a healthier, fairer community for all.

3. LOCAL TARGETS

SPOON thrives on diversity across cities and communities. Here, each CSL defines who to reach and involve — citizens, schools, businesses, local organisations, or policymakers — describing the **audiences that are most relevant** to its goals and context.

Table 2 Stakeholders

Category	Specific Organisation
General public	Public Service Organizations: Avansa
Old people	Specific community/neighbourhood centers (MINTUS)
Vulnerable people/minorities	Neighbourhood centers (Mintus): old people Deelhuis De Dijk: disadvantaged people

Local Authorities	Municipality departments (Climate, environment and nature + care & welfare: neighbourhood centers)
Research Centers	Howest Vives
Food Producers, Processors and Manufacturers	ODAS (tailor-made solutions company; kitchen preparation service; commercial kitchen supplier)

4. ONLINE & OFFLINE CHANNELS

This section presents how the CSL in Bruges plans to engage its audiences through offline channels, such as **local events, collaborations, and campaigns**, and **online channels** - social media, websites, and newsletters.

Table 3 Online Strategy

Channel	Specific Channel	Formats	Target
Website	https://www.brugsfoodlab.be/spoon	Event promotion + subscription to newsletter	General public
Social media	Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/brugsfoodlab/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/BrugsFoodLab	Video posting of our sustainable producer network to inspire people, events promotion	General public
Newsletter		Entire newsletter	General public + stakeholders
Media multipliers	Newsletter of some municipality departments (Climate, environment and Nature)	Newsletter: Brugge naar Morgen	Subscribers to the newsletter: citizens of Bruges

Newsletter of our network organization	Newsletter Republiek	De	Subscribers to the newsletter
Newsletter of Avansa			Subscribers to the newsletter in the region of Bruges (General public)

Table 4 Offline Strategy

Action	Specification
Events	Ex. Social Labs, participation in external conferences, policy roundtables, citizen engagement activities, booths, roadshows
Distribution of materials	Ex. Project flyer, Roll-up, info-sheets, branded gadgets, certificates of attendance, info-sheets
Use of digital materials during events	Ex. Project ppt presentation, project presentation video and pilot videos

POMURJE REGION

1. LOCAL OBJECTIVES AND APPROACH

Each pilot builds on SPOON's mission to make food systems fairer, healthier, and more sustainable. This section highlights the **local goals** and the **participatory approaches** that guide the Lab's work — from citizen engagement and data collection to co-creation activities connecting science with daily life.

The Pomurje CSL aims to **improve consumer food choices** and **food system sustainability** by engaging citizens and local food actors in participatory research, co-creation, and evidence-driven decision making. Pomurje's agrifood identity — rooted in fertile soils, agricultural tradition, and shorter food supply chains — offers a unique real-life context where citizens' everyday choices influence both their health and the resilience of local food systems. The CSL supports increased awareness, trust, and understanding of sustainable, healthy, and **responsible eating habits**, bridging gaps between producers and consumers while aligning supply with actual demand and values.

The CSL adopts a Living Lab and Citizen Science approach to foster co-creation among consumers, producers, retailers, and other stakeholders, collaboratively shaping food environments. It leverages digital tools and traceability systems to gather real-time data on consumer behaviours, preferences, and perceptions, enhancing transparency and evidence-based insights. Through participatory research and engagement activities, it deepens **understanding of consumer needs, motivations, and constraints**, while also designing targeted education and awareness initiatives that promote informed and sustainable food choices. The approach further establishes continuous feedback loops between citizens and local actors, ensuring that insights inform practice and innovation, and integrates behavioural insights into local strategies to guarantee cultural relevance and practical applicability.

2. KEY MESSAGES

Key messages express the **essence of what each pilot aims to communicate**, the core ideas that reflect its purpose within the broader SPOON framework. They should be short, clear, and memorable, capturing the **spirit of the local initiative**. These messages distill the pilot's goals and values into a few key statements that can guide communication across all channels.

Beyond clarity, they should also serve as anchors for a **storytelling approach rooted in the local context**: narratives that reflect the specific culture, needs, and voices of each community. Framing communication through locally grounded stories helps make SPOON's broader objectives tangible and relatable, turning abstract concepts into experiences people can identify with and share.

Communication activities in Pomurje will focus on relatable, everyday food experiences and locally rooted storytelling.

Table 1 Key messages

Local Key Messages
1. Citizens are co-researchers shaping healthier and fairer food systems
2. Everyday food choices matter
3. Local food systems work best when citizens, farmers, and science collaborate
4. Real-life testing helps turn data into practical solutions
5. Purchase and food routine data help improve local food environments

3. LOCAL TARGETS

SPOON thrives on diversity across cities and communities. Here, each CSL defines who to reach and involve — citizens, schools, businesses, local organisations, or policymakers — describing the **audiences that are most relevant** to its goals and context.

Table 2 Stakeholders

Category	Specific Organisation
Citizens	GP F2F LL Consumer Base, Customers of Green Point store
Health actors	Centre for Health Promotion – ZD Murska Sobota
Farmers	Local farmers & demo farms involved in GP F2F LL, Pomurje Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry (KGZMS)
SMEs	Green Point Store, HudoDobro, Vila Natura,
SME representative organisation	Pomurje Chamber of Commerce and Industry
Policymakers	Municipality of Murska Sobota

4. ONLINE & OFFLINE CHANNELS

This section presents how each CSL plans to engage its audiences through offline channels, such as **local events, collaborations, and campaigns**, and **online channels** - social media, websites, and newsletters.

Table 3 Online Strategy

Channel	SpecificChannel	Formats	Target
Website	ITC website; GP F2F LL website	News articles, announcements, event results, summaries	All stakeholders
Social media	GP LikedIn Page; ITC LinekdIn Page; DIH Agrifood LinekdIn Page GR Facebook Page	Social media campaigns, video posting, events promotion, photos, citizen stories	Citizens, SMEs, NGOs
Newsletter	Local Newsletter “Soboške Novine”,	News entry, invitation	Citizens, SMEs, policymakers

	Green Newsletter	Point	
Direct mailings	GP F2F LL Stakeholder mailing lists	Info-packs, invitations	Citizens

Table 4 Offline Strategy

Action	Specification
Events	Any GP F2F LL Event, any DIH Agrifood event
Distribution of materials	Flyers, info-sheets, posters at events
Use of digital materials during events	Presentations, videos, live survey tools at events

THESSALONIKI

1. LOCAL OBJECTIVES AND APPROACH

Each pilot builds on SPOON's mission to make food systems fairer, healthier, and more sustainable. This section highlights the local goals and the participatory approaches that guide the Lab's work — from citizen engagement and data collection to co-creation activities connecting science with daily life.

The Thessaloniki pilot aims to promote **sustainable urban food practices** and support the transition to fairer, healthier, and more resilient local food systems. It focuses on **strengthening local agri-food networks**, improving short supply chains, and **reducing food waste**, while encouraging healthier diets and **equal access to nutritious food**. The pilot also seeks to bring citizens closer to sustainable food choices and reinforce the social and environmental sustainability of the city's food system.

The project combines institutional support from the Municipality of Thessaloniki with community engagement led by Incommon - Kyklos, using participatory and citizen science approaches. It will collect qualitative data on food habits, identify barriers to sustainability, and support local action through workshops, events, and stakeholder collaboration. Building on existing policies and networks, the pilot aims to turn strategy into practical, community-level solutions while strengthening dialogue and shared knowledge among local actors.

2. KEY MESSAGES

Key messages express the **essence of what each pilot aims to communicate**, the core ideas that reflect its purpose within the broader SPOON framework. They should be short, clear, and

memorable, capturing the **spirit of the local initiative**. These messages distill the pilot’s goals and values into a few key statements that can guide communication across all channels.

Beyond clarity, they should also serve as anchors for a **storytelling approach rooted in the local context**: narratives that reflect the specific culture, needs, and voices of each community. Framing communication through locally grounded stories helps make SPOON’s broader objectives tangible and relatable, turning abstract concepts into experiences people can identify with and share.

The overall communication approach of the Thessaloniki pilot focuses on **awareness-raising, empowerment** and reconnection with the city’s food ecosystem. It seeks to bridge the gap between everyday food habits and sustainable alternatives by making local food systems visible, understandable and relevant. Storytelling will serve as a central tool, highlighting real stories from citizens, local producers, markets and neighbourhoods, as well as examples of good practices. Rooted in Thessaloniki’s social, cultural and gastronomic landscape, communication will reflect local habits, challenges and opportunities, translating SPOON’s broader objectives into relatable and actionable narratives for the community.

Table 1 Key messages

Local Key Messages
1. Small everyday food choices, big local impact
2. Together, we shape our city’s food future
3. From our city to our plate
4. Healthy, sustainable, local – everyone's responsibility
5. Know your food. Support local.

3. LOCAL TARGETS

SPOON thrives on diversity across cities and communities. Here, each CSL defines who to reach and involve — citizens, schools, businesses, local organisations, or policymakers — describing the audiences that are most relevant to its goals and context.

Table 2 Stakeholders

Category	Specific Organisation
General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neighborhood of Ano Poli • Citizens of Thessaloniki
Specific group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Care Center for the Elderly - KAPI

Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educators & Trainers (generally) • 45th Primary School of Thessaloniki • 4th Secondary School of Thessaloniki • Environmental Education Centers
Food-related local organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mindful Eating Hellas • Greek Center for Conscious Nutrition • Mamagea
Community initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paramikro • Pervolarides of Thessaloniki • KIPOS 3 project • Social Kitchen of Thessaloniki
Social Cooperative initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trelia Rodia • Koukouli
Food Producers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic Markets Association • Viokofinaki • Chilly Factor Organic Farm
Professionals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local dietitians and nutritionists
Retailers & HORECA sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central Market of Thessaloniki • Local businesses • Local food markets • Eklektik
Food-related Networks & Initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food Saving Alliance Greece • Slow Food Thessaloniki Initiative • Boroume
Research and Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • American Farm School • CERTH – The Centre for Research & Technology • University of Macedonia • Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Local Authorities - Policy Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food Policy Council of Thessaloniki • Municipality's Departments • Social Grocery & Meal Services

4. ONLINE & OFFLINE CHANNELS

This section presents how each CSL plans to engage its audiences through offline channels, such as local events, collaborations, and campaigns, and online channels - social media, websites, and newsletters.

Table 3 Online Strategy

Channel	Specific Channel	Formats	Target
Website	Incommon's website	News updates, event announcements, press releases, and simple downloadable educational resources	General public, educational communities, other NGOs
Website	Municipality of Thessaloniki official website	Important news update for the project, press releases	General public / Residents of Thessaloniki, Local media, Visitors
Social media	Facebook, Instagram (incommon)	Story series, Reels from workshops, short educational explainers (e.g. "What is a short supply chain?"), Social media campaign, event announcements, follow-up posts, Co-created content with local initiatives "Meet the food actors"	General public (urban residents and digitally active audiences), sustainability-oriented citizens, local food actors and community stakeholders.
Social media	Facebook, LinkedIn (Municipality of Thessaloniki - Resilient Thessaloniki)	Formal event invitations, project milestones	Public officers & Municipality staff, Stakeholders, Citizens, External partners
Social media	LinkedIn (Municipality of Thessaloniki)	Formal event invitations, project milestones	Stakeholders, External partners from EU projects

Social media	LinkedIn (Incommon)	Formal event invitations, project milestones	Sustainability Professionals, Educators & Researchers, Stakeholders, External partners from EU projects
Private group	Municipality of Thessaloniki - Food Council of Thessaloniki	Council updates, related initiatives, events and invitations.	Stakeholders, food actors, experts, ngos, activists
Newsletter	Incommon newsletter (SPOON editions)	Workshop insights, calls for participation, good practice examples, exciting news for the project	Thessaloniki based subscribers, Other stakeholders
Media multipliers	Local Media	Dissemination of press releases, journalistic articles, Formal event invitations	Local and national audience
Direct mailings	Direct Mailing list (Municipality of Thessaloniki)	Targeted invitations and official updates	Specific lists of people
Direct mailings	Targeted stakeholder mailing list	Invitations, workshop summaries	Stakeholders, food actors, academia > Participants

Table 4 Offline Strategy

Action	Description
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen Science Lab workshops • Participation in relevant city events and festivals • Participation in external conferences • Policy roundtables

Distribution of materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project flyers • Roll-up banner • Simple info-sheets • QR codes linking to SPOON content • Branded merch (tbc) & fun branded stickers • Certificates of attendance (when needed) • Visibility stickers for collaborating businesses • Permanent visibility poster displayed at the Kyklos space with a clear call-to-action
Use of digital materials during events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project ppt presentation • Project presentation video and pilot videos • Vox pop videos
Other media/activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ongoing citizen engagement through Kyklos space • Local media • Personalized stakeholder meetings • Informal networking moments & presence in local initiatives • Word-of-mouth communication within the community • Communication and cooperation with sister projects
Thematic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Light field visits to local markets and food actors • Micro-gastronomic walk on food loss and waste (tbc)

VALENCIA

1. LOCAL OBJECTIVES AND APPROACH

Each pilot builds on SPOON's mission to make food systems fairer, healthier, and more sustainable. This section highlights the **local goals** and the **participatory approaches** that guide the Lab's work — from citizen engagement and data collection to co-creation activities connecting science with daily life.

The Valencia pilot aims to **promote healthier and more sustainable eating habits** by encouraging behavioural change among citizens, especially **vulnerable groups**. It uses a participatory citizen science approach to collect meaningful data and actively involve people in the research process. The pilot also supports the development of public policies that promote local production, sustainable food systems, and responsible waste management.

Activities will focus on **food purchasing, consumption, and waste**, allowing the collection of real-life data on habits and barriers to sustainable eating. Through collaboration with local organisations, workshops, and participatory methods, citizens will help co-create inclusive and practical solutions. This approach will support the design of effective, community-driven policies that reflect everyday realities and improve Valencia’s food system.

2. KEY MESSAGES

Key messages express the essence of what each pilot aims to communicate, the core ideas that reflect its purpose within the broader SPOON framework. They should be short, clear, and memorable, capturing the spirit of the local initiative. These messages distill the pilot’s goals and values into a few key statements that can guide communication across all channels.

Beyond clarity, they should also serve as anchors for a storytelling approach rooted in the local context: narratives that reflect the specific culture, needs, and voices of each community. Framing communication through locally grounded stories helps make SPOON’s broader objectives tangible and relatable, turning abstract concepts into experiences people can identify with and share.

Valencia's communication approach is grounded in a storytelling narrative that places **citizens at the heart of food system transformation**. By connecting SPOON’s mission with the city’s unique local assets - the Huerta, the Albufera, the Mediterranean Sea, and its rich culinary heritage - the CSL highlights how residents can actively influence a fairer, more sustainable, and more accessible food future. This narrative empowers people by showing that their participation has a tangible impact: through their voices and data, we can gain a better understanding of their needs, identify barriers to sustainable consumption, and co-design meaningful public strategies. Ultimately, our storytelling reinforces the simple message that you can contribute to the change, and you can be part of it.

Table 1 Key messages

Local Key Messages
1. You feed the change.
2. Local Roots. Citizen Power. Real Change.
3. Enjoy Valencia, feed the change or Valencia privilege, citizen power.
4. Empowering citizens, transforming food systems.
5. Together, we grow a healthier Valencia or Together, we shape a sustainable Valencia.

3. LOCAL TARGETS

SPOON thrives on diversity across cities and communities. Here, each CSL defines who to reach and involve - citizens, schools, businesses, local organisations, or policymakers - describing the audiences that are most relevant to its goals and context.

Table 2 Stakeholders

Category	Specific Organisation
General public	<p>Consumer organisations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AVACU • Unió de Consumidors • UNAE <p>Social organisations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Justicia Alimentaria • CERAI. <p>Neighbourhood organisations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Associations in the Grao and Nazaret districts, as well as urban gardening groups. <p>Local media:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Levante TV • À Punt • Valencia Plaza • Levante-EMV
Older people	Municipal senior centres with prior participation in other European projects
Young people	<p>Universities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universitat de València • Universitat Politècnica de València.
Vulnerable people/minorities	<p>Social organisations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cruz Roja • Càritas • UMAE - supporting families at risk of social vulnerability. <p>Municipal Social Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assisting families at risk of social vulnerability who are already beneficiaries of food aid programmes.
Local authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Services of the City of Valencia • Commerce and Markets Departments of the City of Valencia

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mercavalencia • Valencia Smart City
Research Centres	<p>Universities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universitat de València • Universitat Politècnica de València. <p>Think tanks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observatorio del Derecho a la Alimentación de España • Alimentta.
Food Producers, Processors and Manufacturers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small food producers • organic food producers • CAECV
Third sector/ Community initiatives	<p>Social organisations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cruz Roja • Cáritas • UMAE <p>Municipal Social Services</p> <p>Neighbourhood organisations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Associations in the Grao and Nazaret districts (or others), as well as urban gardening groups.

4. ONLINE & OFFLINE CHANNELS

This section presents how the CSL in Valencia plans to engage its audiences through offline channels, such as local events, collaborations, and campaigns, and online channels - social media, websites, and newsletters.

Table 3 Online Strategy

Channel	Specific Channel	Formats	Target
Website	València Innovation Capital website	Website news, press Releases, event promotion	General public, older/ young people, local authorities
Social media	València Innovation Capital social networks	Social media campaigns, events promotion (pre-event	General public, young people, local

			and post-event information)	authorities, research centres
Newsletter	València Innovation Capital agrifood programs database		Entire newsletter	General public, young people, local authorities
Media multipliers	Community local shops/ local City Council services	Centres, markets, administrations, local	Dissemination of press releases, project progress, participation and conclusions of the events	General public, older/ young people, local authorities, food producers
Direct mailings	Dissemination of relevant content to consumers, stakeholders, producers and centres	food research	Best practices book, food diary, training materials	General public, older/ young people, vulnerable people, local authorities, research centres, food producers, third sector

Table 4 Offline Strategy

Action	Specification
Events	Social Citizen Labs, citizen engagement activities, participation in external conferences, policy roundtables
Distribution of materials	Project flyer, roll-up, info-sheets, branded gadgets, certificates of attendance, info-sheets, food diary.
Use of digital materials during events	Project ppt presentation, project presentation video and pilot videos
Other media/activities	Local newspapers

ANNEX 2 – PROJECTS & INITIATIVES MAPPING

Project Name	Country/Region	Funding Programme	Project Status	Thematic Area	Short Description	Potential Synergies with SPOON
ToNoWaste	Europe (7 countries)	Horizon Europe	Ongoing (ends Feb-27)	Food systems (Food Loss and Waste Prevention)	ToNoWaste is a 48-month EU project that unites 21 institutions from seven countries to reduce food loss and waste through a holistic, multi-stakeholder approach. It develops evidence-based tools, open-access data, and innovation ecosystems to help farmers, supply-chain actors, policymakers, and consumers make better decisions for sustainable food production and consumption.	Potential synergies can arise from combining ToNoWaste's evidence-based tools for food-waste prevention with SPOON's citizen-science and behavioural-change approach. Together, they could enhance data quality, empower communities, and co-create more effective strategies for sustainable food systems.
FOOD 2030 Network	Europe	Horizon Europe	Ongoing (ends Dec-26)	Food systems	EU-wide cluster platform driven by the CLEVERFOOD project, connecting projects, networks, and living labs dedicated to transforming food systems toward a fair, healthy, sustainable, and circular future. It supports collaboration, knowledge sharing, and citizen engagement across Europe	FOOD 2030 and SPOON can collaborate through shared living labs, policy and governance initiatives, citizen-engagement tools, data-driven methods, and joint communication efforts to strengthen Europe's transition to sustainable food systems.
DELICIOUS	5 Mediterranean countries (Spain,	PRIMA (Partnership for Research	Completed (Sep-25)	Behavioural Change	DELICIOUS aims to promote healthier and more sustainable Mediterranean diets among children and adolescents by understanding socio-economic and	DELICIOUS and SPOON can align by promoting healthier, sustainable diets through behavioural-change actions. DELICIOUS focuses on

	Portugal, Italy, and Egypt & Lebanon)	and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area)			cultural barriers to adherence. Through behavioural-change actions, school-based education, improved canteen menus, and new Mediterranean snacks, the project encourages better food choices and supports long-term lifestyle shifts	children’s Mediterranean diet habits, while SPOON’s citizen-science BCIs can extend and enrich these approaches across communities
Food Trails	19 European partners	Horizon Europe 2020	Completed (Nov-24)	Food Policy	The project aimed to enable cities to reimagine, develop and implement sustainable, healthy and inclusive food policies. Each partner city ran a pilot project, a “Living Lab,” a space for work, dialogue and collaboration that fostered innovation, connected local key stakeholders, and collected evidence to support urban policy change in food systems. Living Labs sought to co-design and co-implement food actions integrated with other local sectoral work and aligned with the Farm to Fork EU Strategy and the priorities of the EU-FOOD2030 Policy: nutrition, climate, circularity and innovation. The project was rooted in the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP), an international agreement among mayors.	Even though one project has finished, its results, tools, networks, and knowledge can support the implementation of the new SPOON project. A very important tool is the stakeholder network of the previous project. The Use of existing local partnerships to test behavioral change strategies related to food choices or sustainability. In addition, the behavioral change project SPOON can help implement or operationalize the policies proposed by the finished project. And general, in many other ways EU food project can support and frame a food strategy.
foodCLICK	8 CITY REGIONS & 8 BROADENING CITIES	EU Funding Project	On going (2027)	Food Policy - Food Access - Sustainable Food Systems	foodCLICK aims to create sustainable urban food environments. To provide healthy, sustainable, affordable + attractive food to all people. Europe’s urban areas face challenges to ensure availability of healthy, sustainably produced food for all inhabitants and especially for people facing systemic	Policy frameworks are being supported by FoodCLIC can provide the structural context for behavioural interventions in SPOON. SPOON can operationalise and test the impact of food policies. Through citizen science labs and digital tools that collect data on

barriers. Promising initiatives taken by municipalities to change the architecture of food choice often fail to become embedded in the wider policy context and to reach food-deprived and vulnerable groups. FoodCLIC brings together actors from politics, science and civil society to support the development of integrated urban food policies. FoodCLIC wants to ensure that urban planning always incorporates food considerations.

food consumption behaviour, SPOON can generate evidence on how people respond to policy measures such as sustainable diets, food access initiatives or food waste reduction. The two projects can collaborate through shared stakeholder networks and participatory approaches. FoodCLIC strengthens multi-actor food policy networks in city-regions, while SPOON actively involves citizens, researchers and policymakers in co-creating solutions for sustainable food systems. This shared multi-stakeholder ecosystem facilitates knowledge exchange, joint activities and dissemination.

CONSORTIUM

SPOON

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